

Intervention based on the PPCB (Program to Prevent Child Bullying) to reduce bullying in early childhood education

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Abstract

Bullying is a type of violence that occurs among schoolchildren. While this type of behavior is expected in later stages, such as primary and secondary education, it is not surprising that in early childhood, peer behaviors such as rejection, which involve the manifestation of aggressive behavior, occur. Therefore, it is important to understand the sociometric distribution of the class group in order to identify the predominant sociometric types and to implement programs that focus on emotional management and the acquisition of social skills from the early childhood stage. For this reason, the objectives are to evaluate the effectiveness of the program to prevent bullying in early childhood education; to determine the social relationships among students participating in the program; to determine teacher satisfaction after implementing the intervention program and its validity. The materials used are the program used, a field diary, and two questionnaires: a sociometric questionnaire and a teacher assessment questionnaire. The method is a quasi-experimental design, with pre-test and post-test measures and a control group, a waiting list group, and an experimental group, with 57 participants from the second cycle of early childhood education. The results reveal that 38.37% of the total sample falls into the rejected sociometric typology, implying a high percentage of aggression, a risk indicator. It is important to address situations of rejection and aggression from the early stages to promote the development of social and emotional skills such as empathy, respect, and peaceful conflict resolution that will help avoid aggressive situations in later stages.

Keywords:

Bullying, Early Childhood Education, Sociometric Methods, Peer Relationships.

1. Introduction

Bullying occurs at all stages of education, although it is difficult to establish whether it exists in early childhood due to children's unique psycho-developmental characteristics, such as egocentrism, emotional regulation, and social relationships, which are influential factors in the problems that may arise among young children (Moreno & Gregorio, 2018).

Both victims and bullies can suffer negative short- and long-term consequences (Oñate & Piñuel, 2006). Victims may experience mental health problems, low self-esteem, academic difficulties, social isolation, and even suicidal thoughts (Hernández & Solano,

2007). Bullies, for their part, may develop violent behavior patterns and continue to suffer in the future (Hernández, 2005; Arellano, 2008).

Meaningful relationships with peers are vital, so their proper development is highly valuable for fostering diverse learning (Rodríguez-Carrillo et al., 2018). Sometimes, these relationships are inadequate or fail to manifest themselves, which can lead to rejection that affects people's overall well-being (Bradshaw & Richardson, 2009). Aggressive behavior is among the leading causes of rejection among students in childhood, as it reduces status and increases negative emotionality (Bengtsson et al., 2022). For this reason, it is essential to prevent and address bullying from all perspectives: family, school, and social. Therefore, early detection, along with appropriate interventions and support for victims, are key to combating this problem and creating safe and healthy environments for all students (Bartolomé & Díaz, 2020).

In this regard, bullying prevention programs must be developed and implemented, as they are essential for creating safe and positive educational environments where students can thrive academically and emotionally (Gouveia et al., 2017). These programs address bullying holistically, involving students, educators, families, and the community at large (García & Posadas, 2018).

Definition of the concept

Bullying is a type of violence that occurs among students repeatedly and is sustained over time (Olweus, 1998). These behaviors are characterized by the intention of one or more aggressors to humiliate and abusively subjugate a defenseless victim (Enríquez, 2015).

Characteristics of bullying (García & Ascensio, 2015):

- **Intentionality:** The aggressor seeks to harm the victim, whether physically, emotionally, or socially.
- **Repetition:** The bullying acts are repeated over time; they are not isolated incidents (lasting at least 6 months).
- **Power imbalance:** There is a real or perceived difference in power between the aggressor and the victim, whether due to physical strength, age, popularity, etc.
- **Persistence:** The bullying persists over time, causing lasting harm to the victim.

For Soriano (2015), bullying is classified as

- **Physical:** Direct aggression such as hitting, pushing, theft, or damage to belongings.
- **Verbal:** Insults, nicknames, teasing, threats, and humiliating comments.
- **Social:** Exclusion, isolation, malicious rumors, and cyberbullying (bullying through electronic means).
- **Psychological:** Intimidation, blackmail, manipulation, and any action that damages the victim's self-esteem and emotional well-being. This type of bullying is considered the most damaging (Oñate & Piñuel, 2006).

- Cyberbullying: Refers to bullying the victim through the use of ICT tools such as computers, tablets, and mobile phones. It most frequently occurs through the internet or social media.

Importance of bullying prevention programs

According to (Martínez et al., 2024), they focus on the following:

- Significantly reduce its incidence, since raising awareness about the problem, educating about the negative consequences, and promoting positive social skills reduce the likelihood of bullying incidents occurring (Bröder & Carvalho, 2019; Wang et al., 2019).
- Foster a positive school climate, because students feel safe, respected, and valued. Promoting empathy, inclusion, and peaceful conflict resolution fosters a sense of community and belonging, which deters bullying and violence.
- Improve students' emotional well-being by providing them with tools and support to face bullying and develop resilience (Muñoz, 2017).
- Promote the development of social skills through the components they include, such as effective communication, conflict resolution, empathy, and respect (Estrada et al., 2023).
- Involve the entire educational community (students, educators, parents, and other members) in creating a safe and supportive environment. By working together, a more significant and sustainable impact can be achieved (Llorent et al., 2021).

Taking social relationships as a key element for improving students' emotional well-being, Rohner & Carrasco (2014) determined that peer rejection is a negative factor for children's emotional well-being, leading to future maladjustment and a risk marker for aggressive behavior.

Since inclusion in classrooms is the best way to achieve group cohesion and, therefore, improve the social climate, students who are rejected should be identified in order to address this issue in the classroom and prevent future aggressive behavior (Stites et al., 2018).

For this purpose, sociograms are appropriate constructs that indicate social relationships within a group. Specifically, they indicate whether a student is liked or rejected by their peers, with rejection being the negative factor corresponding to the number of nominations received in that category (Greco, 2019). The use of this technique is invaluable in bullying prevention due to its ability to visualize and analyze social dynamics within a group, as it detects risk situations such as rejected, isolated, and leader students (Hurtado & Cárdenas, 2018).

Furthermore, it assesses the degree of cohesion among group members, as well as the presence of subgroups or internal divisions. It detects conflicts and problems and helps identify potential dilemmas in interpersonal relationships. It also intervenes in bullying situations by revealing patterns of rejection or isolation toward certain group members (Ruiz et al., 2013).

For the above reasons, this research, this research aims to: evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention program against bullying in early childhood education using literature; determine the social relationships among students participating in the program; and determine teacher satisfaction after implementing the intervention program and its validity.

2. Materials and Methods

This is a quasi-experimental design, with pre-test and post-test measures and a control group, a waiting list group, and an experimental group (Creswell, 2012).

The respective permits were obtained from two educational centers, along with the duly signed informed consent of the families. The study also complied with the Declaration of Helsinki and Organic Law 3/2018, of December 5, on the Protection of Personal Data and the Guarantee of Digital Rights, as well as the approval of the Ethics Committee of the University of Jaén (Reference: MAR.23/11 TES).

2.1. Sample

The sample consisted of 57 subjects (30 boys and 27 girls) divided into three groups, each from the second cycle of early childhood education for children aged 4 to 5, from two public schools in the province of Jaén. All students from the schools where the protocol was followed participated.

2.2. Instruments

To conduct this study and evaluate its results, a field diary was used to collect data during the sessions, as well as two scientifically validated instruments.

The field diary is an essential instrument used by researchers in various disciplines to record observations, experiences, and data during fieldwork (Luna et al., 2022).

The Sociometric Peer Nomination Questionnaire (González & García-Bacete, 2010), used in the pre-test and post-test phases (SOCIOMET), provides information on the five classroom sociometric types: preferred (low aggression), rejected (high aggression), ignored (low aggression), controversial (some aggression), and average (some aggression). The results are sociometric type and the number of positive (NPR) and negative (NNR) nominations received. It also provides individual and group relative indices, comparable among them, such as the positive nominations received (INPR: percentage of colleagues who nominate you positively, and who identify with a measure of individual attractiveness), and the negative nominations received (INNRR: percentage of colleagues who nominate you negatively and indicate the degree of individual antipathy).

The Teacher Evaluation Questionnaire (Molinero et al., 2023) was conducted on teachers to determine their satisfaction with the intervention program. It contains three open-ended questions, the responses to which are transcribed, and the results are evaluated. The questions are:

1. What skills do you think have been most promoted among your students with the program?
2. What are the greatest advantages you found in this study?
3. What are the greatest difficulties you encountered in this study?

And nine closed-ended questions applied to a 4-point Likert-type scale, with 1 being "strongly disagree" and 4 being "strongly agree." The scale items are as follows:

1. I found knowing the sociometric distribution of my classroom interesting.
2. I consider the data provided about my students useful.
3. I have acquired new knowledge about rejection.
4. The activities were compatible with my class sessions.
5. The researcher's disposition was positive.
6. The activities and strategies implemented are useful to prevent and reduce rejection.
7. The organization of the activity sheets is useful.
8. I would participate in the study again.
9. The study has met my previous expectations.

2.3. Procedure

The study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the University of Jaén (MAR.23/11 TES). The program was validated by 11 experts from different Spanish universities and various specialties, with the modifications indicated by these experts being made. Furthermore, the program obtained the favorable approval of the participating schools and the informed consent of the families of the aforementioned schools.

The schools were randomly selected from among those who responded affirmatively to participation. They have similar characteristics; they are public schools located in different towns in the province of Jaén, whose families are middle-class.

Briefing sessions were held with the directors of both schools, as well as with the tutors of the stage chosen for the research. In these sessions, information was obtained about the class group climate with which they would work and they were given information about the program that would be implemented, as well as about the phenomenon of bullying, the technique used to measure social relationships in the class group, its sociometric types, causes, consequences, and student profiles.

In these sessions, the information collected indicates that, in group 1 (G1), the tutor reported problems with ongoing aggression among students, but this did not occur in

group 2 (G2). This determined the method used to implement the program to compare its effectiveness among groups exhibiting conflictive behaviors.

Initially, the pre-test assessment was conducted on three groups. The program was then implemented in the experimental group (G1). The program consists of activities that focus on emotional intelligence, social skills, and/or teamwork through children's literature (Agudo & Cachón, 2025). Once completed, a sociometric assessment was conducted on the three groups to compare the results.

The program was conducted on the waiting list group (G2), and the sociometric assessment was again conducted on all three groups. The objective was to verify whether the program had been effective in G2 and to determine whether the results obtained in G1 were maintained over time.

The program was not conducted on the control group (G3) in order to compare the results with the experimental and waiting-list groups.

The study was conducted in three phases:

1) Initial session (pre-test): in which the sociometric assessment was conducted on the sample (one experimental group, one waiting-list group, and one control group).

2) The intervention program was conducted on G1 and G2 in 10 sessions (3 months) organized for each group, with one session per week. The first and last sessions are for evaluation. However, it is a flexible proposal open to possible variations in time or content. As the program is designed for children in early childhood education, the program uses didactic, fun, and participatory methods, using a comprehensive approach that offers meaningful learning (Hernández & De Barros, 2013), in which children acquire knowledge based on what they already have in their cognitive structure (Moreira, 2020). It's about making children the protagonists of their own learning, encouraging them to express their opinions and take their own initiative.

The sessions used children's literature as the main teaching tool, which helps develop emotional intelligence, as literature is a powerful source of values and principles for early childhood education (Mata, 2014).

3) Final session (post-test): sociometric evaluation of the three groups after the program execution and data collection from the tutors' satisfaction questionnaire.

Pre-test data collection was conducted during the school year, always by the same person to avoid cross-contamination. Individual responses were conducted in a noise-free environment and in alphabetical order.

A sociometric peer nomination questionnaire was used, which asked the questions: "Who are the three classmates you choose as your best friends? Why?" and "Who are the three classmates you least like as friends? Why?" to determine positive and negative nominations.

Statistical analysis to determine acceptance and rejection rates was carried out using Microsoft Excel software, using the Mode measure of central position to obtain the value of the variable with the highest absolute frequency and to identify the most frequently occurring values.

Subsequently, to determine the sociometric types, the reasons for the nominations, and the changes in the pre-test and post-test, the mean of the individual values of negative and positive nominations received was calculated for each subject, and distributed equally among all students in the group. To define the different sociometric types, positive nominations received (PNR) were used, which has an upper limit of 5.7 and a mean of 2.9, while negative nominations received (NNR) has an upper limit of 5.8 and a mean of 3.0. Regarding the data obtained from the field diary, the results indicate a gradual integration of the participant sample into the activities, with the initial sessions experiencing more difficulty interacting with the participants due to the unknown staff. As the sessions progressed, direct observation showed how the students improved their interpersonal relationships with their peers through dialogue, thereby reducing aggressive behavior if an altercation arose between classmates.

Finally, a frequency analysis was conducted to determine the faculty's opinions of the program.

3. Results

The sociometric distribution of each group in the evaluation of the different phases is reflected in Tables 1, 2, and 3 and Figures 1, 2, and 3.

The results identified in the pre-test measures of G1 and G2 do not resemble those obtained in the study by Molinero et al. (2023), where there is a sociometric distribution composed of 13.6% preferred students, 9.1% ignored students, 2.3% controversial students, 11.4% rejected students, and 63.6% average students.

Grouping the sociometric typologies into rejected and non-rejected, in the pre-test measures, it is observed that in G1 there is a 9.09% of rejected (90.91% of non-rejected) compared to 18.75% of rejected in G2 and 10.53% of rejected in G3 (see tables 1 and 2 and graphs 1 and 2). These data contradict those obtained in the information session with the tutor of G1 where she expressed major social problems in her classroom, nor do they correspond with the information obtained from the tutor of G2 who stated that there were no social problems in her class group.

In the sociometric typology of rejected students identified in the pre-test, it is observed that in G1 there are 2 students, of whom, after the post-test, one remains rejected and the other moves to the average typology. In G2, 3 students are observed as rejected, 2 of whom remain rejected and one moves to average (see Table 4). Finally, in G3, the variation varies throughout its measurements, with 2 students in the rejected typology in the first measurement, which increases in the second measurement, leaving 3 students in the rejected typology and the last measurement with 4 students in the same typology (see Table 3). Therefore, there are changes in the nominations that are greater in the

percentages of negative nominations, which can be verified with the index of positive nominations received (INPR) and with the index of negative nominations received (INNP) for the 2 students of G1 and the 3 students of G2, which are the percentage of the total nominations in the classroom (see table 4).

Furthermore, it is observed that in G1, in the measurement to verify the program's effectiveness (3 months after the intervention), the values for the INNR and INPR vary non-significantly when the measurement is repeated, remaining in the rejected category at 4.54% (see Table 1 and Graph 3).

Table 1

Sociometric distribution G1 (experimental)

Sociometric type	1st measurement %	2nd measurement %	3rd measurement %
Preferred	9.09	4.55	4.54
Rejected	9.09	4.55	4.54
Controversial	0	4.55	4.54
Ignored	27.7	27.27	31.82
Medium	54.55	59.09	54.55

Legend: preferred (low aggression), rejected (high aggression), controversial (some aggression), ignored (low aggression), average (some aggression). The results are sociometric and the number of positive (NPR) and negative (NNR) nominations received.

Table 2

Sociometric distribution G2 (waiting list)

Sociometric type	1st measurement %	2nd measurement %	3rd measurement %
Preferred	18.75	18.75	12.50
Rejected	12.50	18.75	12.50
Controversial	0	0	0
Ignored	18.75	18.75	18.75
Medium	50.00	43.75	56.25

Table 3

Sociometric distribution G3 (control)

Sociometric type	1st measurement %	2nd measurement %	3rd measurement %
Preferred	10.53	10.53	26.31
Rejected	10.53	15.78	21.05
Controversial	5.26	0	0
Ignored	15.79	15.78	26.31
Medium	57.89	57.89	26.31

Table 4

Positive nominations (NPR), positive nomination index (INPR), negative nominations (NNR), and negative nomination index (INNR) received before and after the intervention.

Group		NPRpre (INPRpre)	NPRpos (INPRpos)	NNRpre (INNRpre)	NNRpos (INNRpos)
G1	Student 1	3 (5%)	0 (0%)	11 (18.33)	8 (13.33%)
G1	Student 2	0 (0%)	2 (3.55%)	6 (10%)	5 (8.33%)
G2	Student 1	1 (2.08%)	1 (2.08%)	9 (18.75%)	7 (14.58%)
G2	Student 2	2 (4.17%)	2 (4.17%)	11 (22.92%)	10 (20.83%)
G2	Student 3	2 (4.17%)	3 (6.25%)	4 (8.33%)	0 (0%)

Regarding the reasons given by the groups to determine the NPR (INPR) and NNR (INNR), they were classified according to the following codes (Tables 5, 6, and 7): a) friends, b) affinity for games, c) hitting, d) helping, e) not socializing, f) not allowing the child to play, g) gets angry and annoying, h) is very good, i) lacks affinity for games, j) is mean, k) are family, l) is of the opposite sex.

According to the reasons related to physical aggression, it is observed that in G1 the percentage increases by 11.66% after the program was implemented, increasing by 35% in the follow-up evaluation carried out with this center after 3 months to determine its effectiveness. This shows that, despite the reduction in the percentage of those rejected in the classroom, aggression continues to occur, coinciding with what Bengtsson et al. (2022) reported. This percentage increase is not observed in G2, as there is a 12.5% decrease in the response to aggression.

Table 5

Distribution of reasons for NPR and NNR: G 1 (experimental)

Code answers	NPRpre (INPRpre-test) %	NPRpost (INPRpost-test) %	NNRpre (INNRpre-test) %	NNRpost (INNRpost-test) %
a	13 (21.67)	8 (13.33)	0 (0)	0 (0)
b	35 (58.33)	37 (61.66)	0 (0)	1 (1.67)
c	0 (0)	0 (0)	24 (40.00)	31 (51.66)
d	5 (8.33)	6 (10.00)	0 (0)	12 (20.00)
e	0 (0)	0 (0)	12 (20)	0 (0)
f	0 (0)	0 (0)	5 (8.33)	1 (1.67)
g	0 (0)	0 (0)	15 (25)	6 (10.00)
h	3 (5)	6 (10.00)	0 (0)	0 (0)
i	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	5 (8.33)
j	0 (0)	0 (0)	4 (6.66)	4 (6.66)
k	4 (6.66)	3 (5)	0 (0)	0 (0)
l	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)

Table 6

Distribution of reasons for NPR y NNR: G 2 (waiting list)

Code answers	NPRpre (INPRpre-test) %	NPRpost (INPRpost-test) %	NNRpre (INNRpre-test) %	NNRpost (INNRpost-test) %
a	16 (33.33)	9 (18.75)	0 (0)	0 (0)
b	25 (52.08)	31 (64.58)	0 (0)	0 (0)
c	0 (0)	0 (0)	11 (22.92)	5 (10.42)
d	3 (6.25)	4 (8.33)	0 (0)	0 (0)
e	0 (0)	0 (0)	15 (31.25)	15 (31.25)
f	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3 (6.25)
g	0 (0)	0 (0)	5 (10.42)	5 (10.42)
h	4 (8.33)	4 (8.33)	0 (0)	0 (0)
i	0 (0)	0 (0)	5 (10.42)	5 (10.42)
j	0 (0)	0 (0)	9 (18.75)	15 (31.25)
k	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
l	0 (0)	0 (0)	3 (6.25)	0 (0)

Table 7

Distribution of reasons for NPR y NNR: G 3 (control)

Code answers	NPRpre (INPRpre-test) %	NPRpost (INPRpost-test) %	NNRpre (INNRpre-test) %	NNRpost (INNRpost-test) %
a)	5 (8.47)	8 (14.04)	0 (0)	0 (0)
b)	42 (71.18)	40 (70.18)	0 (0)	0 (0)
c)	0 (0)	0 (0)	15 (26.31)	19 (33.33)
d)	2 (3.39)	2 (3.51)	0 (0)	0 (0)
e)	0 (0)	0 (0)	22 (38.6)	14 (24.56)
f)	0 (0)	0 (0)	4 (7.02)	9 (15.79)
g)	2 (3.39)	0 (0)	8 (14.04)	7 (12.28)
h)	7 (11.86)	5 (8.77)	0 (0)	0 (0)
i)	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (3.51)	1 (1.75)
j)	0 (0)	0 (0)	6 (10.53)	7 (12.28)
k)	1 (1.69)	2 (3.51)	0 (0)	0 (0)
l)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)

Regarding the data obtained from the teacher satisfaction questionnaire, they indicated that the greatest skills they believe the program has promoted among their students are: in G1, empathy, assertiveness, and helping others; and in G2, camaraderie, tolerance, respect, and equality.

The greatest advantages they have found in the development of the study have been: in G1, using stories, as it is an engaging way for students to assimilate certain difficult-to-understand situations, such as emotional adjustment in social relationships; and promoting cooperative work and group cohesion in a playful manner and through a

participatory methodology adapted to the student level, thereby improving social relationships among students in G2.

Regarding the greatest difficulties encountered in this study, in G1, reaching all students, since the class group was very diverse, and in G2, the limited classroom space for carrying out certain activities.

The assessment of the study carried out by the tutor teachers of G1 and G2 regarding the Likert scale found positive data, scoring the study overall at 4/4.

4. Discussion

Bullying situations are often overlooked in early childhood education, occurring more frequently in primary and secondary education (Oñate & Piñuel, 2006). The fact that social relationships and group cohesion are key to fostering appropriate peer behavior is downplayed (López & Frutos, 2011).

However, the data obtained in this study indicate the need to implement bullying prevention programs starting in early childhood education, in line with Hanish et al. (2021). This can be confirmed by the data obtained regarding the sociometric typologies of the participating groups, with a percentage of 38.37% of the total rejected students in the pre-test across the three groups.

The results obtained are similar to those of other research, such as that of Nergaard (2020), who believes that peer rejection appears in an early age and is a risk indicator of aggressive behavior in the future (Hanish et al., 2021). Given that bullies tend to have an aggressive and dominant profile (Yue & Zhang, 2023), it is vitally important to work on social skills, emotional intelligence, and group cohesion from early childhood education to prevent rejection and, therefore, aggressive behavior in later stages, in line with Mateu-Martínez et al. (2013).

This study agrees with the results obtained for the sociometric typologies of rejected, preferred, and average children in the pre-test, as well as with those of the research conducted by Ortega et al. (2013), where 12.75% of children are nominated as rejected, 76.6% as average, and 10.65% as preferred, which demonstrates a similarity in behaviors at early stages.

Regarding the reasons for rejection or preference by peers, a total of 12 reasons were obtained: 5 for acceptance and 7 for rejection. The reasons for acceptance are categorized as best friends, playmates, helpfulness, kindness, and kinship, while those for rejection outnumber those for acceptance and are categorized as physical aggression, lack of playmates, lack of interaction, not allowing each other to play, anger and annoyance, being mean, and, lastly, not belonging to the same sex. The classification of the reasons collected in this research is similar to those obtained in the study conducted by Martín et al. (2024).

The program applied in this research focuses on promoting empathy, assertiveness, and emotional intelligence through children's literature, since this tool encourages cooperative work, listening, values, respect, and tolerance, essential aspects to enhance the comprehensive development of the child from an early age (Martínez, 2019). Through its

application, teachers now understand their students' social relationships, and that rejection is a risk factor for aggression in the present and in the future, in line with Rohner & Carrasco (2014). They have also been offered effective tools to work on the prevention/eradication of aggressive behaviors through emotional intelligence, given that the teachers have reported positive results after the interventions carried out, in line with the results obtained by Fuerte (2022), who determined that 68% of early childhood education teachers who incorporated emotional intelligence into their practices observed a decrease in bullying in their classrooms.

5. Conclusions

After the program's implementation and evaluation, the percentage of rejection types and negative nominations received by students was reduced. Its effectiveness was also demonstrated after its follow-up evaluation for G1, given that the data on negative nominations for rejected students in this group did not show significant variation.

Regarding the determination of the social relationships among the participating students in the pre-test, grouping the sociometric typologies into rejected and non-rejected, it is observed that in G1, 9.09% were rejected (90.91% non-rejected) compared to 18.75% in G2 (81.25% non-rejected) and 10.53% in G3 (89.47% non-rejected), indicating the possibility of aggressive behavior among students.

Finally, teachers' assessments were obtained, the results of which reveal 100% satisfaction with the program, indicating that its implementation has promoted values such as empathy, assertiveness, helping others, camaraderie, tolerance, respect, and equality. They stated that the advantages they found with the program were the successful use of the teaching tool (children's literature) as well as the playful and cooperative methodology that encompasses the entire program, which leads to group cohesion and improved social relationships among students.

Regarding the difficulties encountered in this study, the teachers expressed the impossibility of reaching all students given the diversity of the class group and the limited classroom space for certain activities.

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